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The Circular Economy

In Practice-focused Undergraduate Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

The growth of the planet's population makes the traditional industrial model of "take, make and waste" unsustainable. The circular economy, in which resources are continuously reused, offers a solution. For manufacturers of durable goods the circular economy requires a well-functioning circular supply chain that includes reverse logistics, product recovery operations, development of markets for recovered products, and integration of reuse and product recovery into the firm's daily operations. How to educate undergraduate practice-focused engineers in the design, implementation, and operation circular supply chains is un-explored and the purpose of the paper is to identify a suitable teaching method. Because courses in circular supply chain topics are currently non-existent, the paper first develops a set of learning goals based on the skillset necessary to design, implement, and operate a circular supply chain. Second, the paper examines whether the teaching method of a similar cross-disciplinary course in innovation can be successfully applied. This teaching method is based on cross-disciplinary team projects that work with innovation in cooperation with a participating firm. The study concludes that the teaching method can be (largely) applied. However, future research should test the paper's results with studies using data from circular supply chain courses.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education, University-Business cooperation, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Circular economy, circular supply chains, engineering education, undergraduate education

INTRODUCTION

The traditional “take, make and waste” industrial model first extracts resources from the planet (e.g. in quarries, mines, the ocean, farmlands and woods). Second, the model turns these resources into materials, components, and products, which are used and then discarded. Finally, discarded products end their life in scrapyards or as CO₂ resulting from either decay or incineration. With the growth of the planet’s overall population and the increasing middle-class population, this traditional industrial model makes resource scarcity one of the planet’s greatest future challenges. An emerging concept that offers a solution to the resource scarcity challenge is the circular economy, in which resources are continuously reused (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015a). In addition to solving the planet’s resource scarcity problem, reuse offers firms a wide array of business opportunities (e.g. Larsen and Jacobsen, 2016).

The circular economy concept covers circular routes for products, components and materials. Among these circular routes are sharing resources (cars and production equipment), repairing functioning products, refurbishing and remanufacturing products, and recycling of materials. For manufacturers of durable goods the circular economy requires a well-functioning circular supply chain that includes reverse logistics, product recovery operations, development of markets for recovered products, and integration of reuse and product recovery into the firm’s daily operations. In a study from the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2015b) the primary barrier for implementing and operating circular supply chains in the manufacturing sector is the lack of skills, capabilities, and the basic knowledge of the possibilities inherent in circular supply chains. The antidote to overcome these barriers is education. Education can provide these lacking skills and capabilities to future employees of all kinds. Engineers have the perhaps greatest influence on product and process design and work with both implementation and operation of processes. Therefore, providing engineers with the skills and capabilities to design, implement, and operate circular supply chains will deliver a competence base that supports a transition towards the circular economy.

Extant literature within engineering education does not prescribe how educational systems can effectively provide students with the necessary skills to design, implement, and operate circular supply chains. Searching the digital library of the Technical University of Denmark using the search string (circular AND "engineering education") results in 183 hits. The library’s search engine searches in both academic databases and conference proceedings. One paper among the 182 hits explicitly concerns circular supply chain education. This paper written by Pereira and Frederiksson (2015), which is part of the conference proceedings of the 43rd SEFI Conference, discusses the use CES EduPack in teaching evaluation of resource usage. The paper focuses on milk bottle reuse. A few other papers resulting from the search discuss resource usage in the built environment. The search leads this study to conclude that that the question of how to educate engineers in the design, implementation and operation of circular supply chains is under-researched.

The study adds to the understanding of engineering education within the circular supply chain discipline by examining how universities can facilitate learning of the design, implementation, and operation of circular supply chains.

The study will specifically examine how the subject can be taught within a 10 ECTS-point course frame, corresponding to one third of semester student work load. The study focuses on undergraduate practice-oriented engineering educations. Therefore, the study focuses on teaching methods that integrate a high level of industry involvement.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 1 will extract a set of learning goals for a 10 ECTS course from a literature based understanding of the

circular supply chain. Section 2 will detail the methodology for how the study evaluates teaching methods for the course. Section 3 conducts an analysis of a potentially useful teaching method and discusses the applicability of this teaching method for the 10 ECTS credit course about the circular supply chain. Sections 4-5 discuss results and provides future research suggestions and conclusions.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section will first define the circular supply chain and its constituent components through circular supply chain literature. Second, from this definition of the circular supply chain, the section will extract the necessary skillset that enables practice-focused undergraduate engineering students to design, implement, and operate circular supply chains. Third, from the skillset the section will develop a set of learning goals for a 10 ECTS credit course. The later sections of the paper will use these learning goals to examine a suitable teaching method for the course.

1.1 The circular supply chain

For manufacturers of recoverable products the circular supply chain consists of two overall components: the forward supply chain and the circular supply chain (Larsen *et al.*, 2017). Figure 1 illustrates these two supply chains. The forward supply chain begins with materials manufacturing and component fabrication, continues with finished product assembly and ends with marketing products to customers. The circular supply chain begins with acquiring used products from the market. The circular supply chain then moves these products from customer locations two the firm’s inspection and sorting facility. Products sorted for recovery are recovered and remarketed.

Fig. 1. The circular supply chain (adapted from Larsen et al., 2017)

The circular supply chain circular supply chain can conduct several functions for the firms simultaneously. Figure 2 shows a circular supply chain that conducts the following five functions: 1. Refurbishment of end-products for resale in primary markets as a low-cost version of the virgin product, 2. Refurbishment of end-products for resale in secondary markets, 3. Refurbishment of components for reuse in refurbished products, 4. Refurbishment of components for resale as spare-parts in the aftermarket, 5. Resale of core materials upstream in the supply chain to current suppliers of virgin materials.

Fig. 2. A five-function circular supply chain (adapted from Larsen, 2017)

1.2 The necessary skillset for engineers

The variety in necessary tasks to design, implement and operate a circular supply chain as depicted in Figure 2 requires a skillset that transcends the curricula of any individual engineering education (chemical engineering, civil engineering, mechanical engineering, etc.). Operating a successful circular supply chain requires skills in logistics and production processes, purchasing, developing potential new markets, as well as risk assessment and product design. A course that facilitates learning of this skillset must therefore contain a set of learning goals as the following set in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Learning goals for circular supply chain course

#	Learning goals <i>The course should enable the student to:</i>	Traditional engineering education that relates closest to learning goal
1	Understand how product design impacts product disassemblability, recoverability, and ability to function through several use cycles	Mechanical and electrical engineering
2	Design logistical systems that can take back used products and deliver them at the firm's facility	Manufacturing engineering
3	Identify the whereabouts of the firm's installed base of products, which constitutes the pool of input for the circular supply chain	Information and systems engineering
4	Select and develop manufacturing technologies and processes for recovery of products and components (e.g. refurbishing or remanufacturing processes)	Manufacturing engineering
5	Develop markets for recovered products and components	Export and marketing engineering
6	Identify and implement business models that fit with take-back and recovery processes	Business development engineering
7	Understand the managerial and financial impact of circular supply chains on the firm's profit and competitive strategy	Business development engineering
8	Managing the daily operation of logistical, manufacturing, and sales processes	Manufacturing and business engineering
9	Work in cross-disciplinary teams with members from different engineering backgrounds	All engineering degrees

10	Interact with a firm for the purpose of scoping a project, gaining access to data, cooperating with firm employees in e.g. workshops and problem solving	All engineering degrees
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2 RESEARCH DESIGN

The emergent nature of the circular economy (and circular supply chains in particular) means that experience in teaching the subject is currently non-existent. This eliminates the traditional research method of studying teaching methods in previous circular supply chain courses. Therefore, the study will instead examine the teaching methods used in teaching a topic that is similar to circular supply chain design, implementation and operation. This is the topic of innovation. The study has chosen to study the teaching method of an innovation course for three reasons: 1) universities have a much longer experience in teaching innovation than circular supply chains, 2) teaching innovation often occurs through the use of team-based projects conducted in cooperation with industry, and 3) innovation usually demands cross-disciplinary cooperation across engineering education programs. Among the cross-disciplinary innovation skills are idea generation, conceptualization, technical problem solving and commercialization. Innovation is often taught through cross-disciplinary projects that deliver useful results for the participating firms from industry.

Specifically, the paper examines the teaching method of a large scale innovation course at the Technical University of Denmark labelled “Innovation Pilot”. The study evaluates whether the teaching method applied in this course can be successfully applied to teaching design, implementation, and operation of circular supply chains. Figure 3 depicts the study’s research method. The study evaluates whether the teaching method used in the innovation course aligns with the learning goals of the circular supply chain course in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Research method

3 CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

This section will first describe the learning goals of the Innovation Pilot course; second, the course’s teaching method; and third, the section will evaluate whether the teaching method can be successfully applied in a course with the learning goals in Table 1.

3.1 The learning goals of the Innovation Pilot course

The Innovation Pilot course has among others learning goals related to collection of diverse sorts of information, developing products to fit defined needs and specifications, considering an idea’s or concept’s implementation requirements as well as financial impact and customer perspectives. The students will learn basic theories about business and management, conduct interdisciplinary cooperation in a project context, and cooperate with a pre-selected firm

The Innovation pilot course differs from a course about circular supply chain design, implementation and operation in two particular ways. 1. In the innovation pilot course students begin the project with a completely open problem definition, while the circular supply chain course is limited to circular supply chains. 2. The innovation course focuses (most often) on developing a sellable product or service, while the circular supply chain course focuses on developing a set of processes.

3.2 The teaching method of the Innovation Pilot course

The course has around 250-400 students per semester. Before the course begins an industry coordinator, who works exclusively with this course, has engaged firms willing to participate in the course with one or more cases. The cases are open-ended, but are defined so the firm benefit from participating.

Students divide themselves into groups, which must be cross-disciplinary, and choose a case from a firm. Two or three groups work on the same case. Every Wednesday from 8 am to 17 pm the students are present either at the university working on their case, visiting their case firm, or conducting research with e.g. customers or potential users.

The students learn basic theory of the course via e-learning (YouTube videos) or through traditional text reading. Watching videos or reading texts is done at home as preparation prior to class participation. During the semester, students spend each Wednesday with workshops, where students learn theory active learning (e.g. idea pitching or feedback sessions). During the first weeks of the course, the students work on a “training case” used for the purpose of learning theory. The training case is labelled “the first loop”. For the training case the work period is short and expectations are lower than for the following second loop. For the second loop the students begin working on their selected case. During the second loop period, the students meet with the firm a number several times. Three of these firm-student interactions are formal meetings: At meeting no. 1 the firm present their case, at meeting no. 2 students present their take on the problem that needs solving, and at meeting no. 3 students present their solution and prototype for the firm. The students receive access to relevant data through a contact person at the firm. The course is evaluated through a multiple choice test of e-learning videos and an assessment of a final presentation of the project, which includes a prototype. Table 2 summarizes the elements of the teaching method in the Innovation Pilot course.

Table 2. Elements in the teaching method of the Innovation Pilot course

#	Elements of teaching method
1	Cross-disciplinary teams of students from all engineering degrees
2	Agreements with participating firms prior to the course beginning
3	Development of cases in cooperation with firms prior to the course beginning
4	Learning of basic knowledge through e-learning (YouTube videos) prior to class
5	Problem-based project work that represents most of the students' workload
6	Structured learning flow beginning with training period followed by the core work
7	Continuous interaction between students and case firm for e.g. data collection
8	Evaluation of both basic theory knowledge and the deliverables of the project

3.3 Evaluation of teaching method for a circular supply chain course

The purpose of the course that this study seeks to identify a suitable teaching method for concerns the design, implementation, and operation of circular supply chains. Table

1 presents the learning objectives of the course, while Table 2 summarizes the teaching method of the Innovation Pilot course.

Table 1 shows great disciplinary variety within the set of learning goals, which requires cross-disciplinary student skills. The table shows that the ideal project group consists of five students: one manufacturing engineer, one mechanical engineer, one export/marketing engineer, one business engineer, and one information or data management engineer. Element no. 1 in Table 2 facilitates having cross-disciplinary skills embedded in each project team, but the circular supply chain course must apply a stricter group formation rule to ensure groups with the particular skillset presented in the previous sentence.

The students learn basic theory through YouTube videos and tradition written texts. Students prepare prior to class. The subject matter will change from innovation related subjects to circular supply chain related subjects. However, the range of subjects between innovation and circular supply chain overlap considerably, which suggest that requiring undergraduate engineering students to learn basic theory as preparation for classes is possible without much teacher guidance. Examples of subject matter topics are cost-benefit calculations, basic business understanding, market research skills, product design principles, teamwork, and industry cooperation. A circular supply chain course could adopt this method, but could also use the traditional method of reading articles and book chapters as preparation and then conducting active learning style classroom teaching for deeper learning of theory application.

Working with the design, implementation, and operation of circular supply chains requires the same type of cross-disciplinary team cooperation as innovation. In addition, both courses require involvement of industry. The innovation course integrates industrial firms as project customers and students primary workload concerns fulfilling the need of firm. An industry coordinator identifies firms prior to the course's beginning and each firm expects value from participating. This method can work for the circular supply chain course. However, while the innovation course has considerable amounts of freedom concerning the direction of each project, the circular supply chain course has a predetermined goal from the beginning (the design and implementation of a circular supply chain).

The evaluation form of the innovation course can be directly applied with the circular supply chain course because project groups deliver a supply chain design and implementation plan, while individual students' knowledge of basic theory can be evaluated through a multiple choice test.

4 DISCUSSION, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE RESEARCH SUGGESTION

The ideal dataset for examining the effectiveness of a teaching method contains detailed descriptions of teaching methods, exam results, assessments of long term retention of the course's content, and measurements of a student's ability to apply the content of the course. In 3-4 years this data may be available for courses in circular supply design, implementation and operation.

One particular challenge for the course is how to ensure that students can meet the learning goals that are not directly related to their individual engineering degree. For example, how can the course ensure that a business development engineer learns to design a logistical system, when the group includes a manufacturing engineer, who already possesses expertise in logistical systems design? This problem differs from the innovation course where the innovation discipline is new to most students. How to solve this problem with the course's teaching method is suggested for future research as well. The problem may be researched already, so a review of the literature may yield useful results.

5 CONCLUSION

The question that this study has answered concerns how universities can facilitate learning of the design, implementation, and operation of circular supply chains. The study has examined whether the teaching method of a similar course in innovation can be successfully applied, the study's results suggest that it can. Table 2 summarizes the method. However, the method needs one addition concerning how to handle situations where students perform only the tasks they already master from their own education at the expense learning other tasks in the design, implementation and operation of the circular supply chain.

In addition to proving insights into how universities can teach design, implementation and operation of circular supply chains, the study's results are expected to contribute to theory about effective teaching of cross-disciplinary subjects that require a high degree of industry involvement (e.g. close industry-university relations and positive outcomes for students and participating firms).

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Since we are using double-blind reviewing process, also references revealing the identity of the author(s) should be made anonymous until the final paper.

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